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IV: The Racial Contract and the Case for Epistemic Marxism

In the opening pages of his book, *The Racial Contract*, Charles W. Mills introduces his masterful argument that “White Supremacy is the unnamed political system that has made the modern world what it is today.”⁵⁴ He theorizes that there exists a contract that is conceptually prior to the primary social contract establishing society that has the sole purpose of maintaining the primacy of white peoples over nonwhites throughout much of the world. He argues that this theory is explanatorily superior to those of traditional contractarians both in its historical actuality and normative principles.⁵⁵

In its current state, there is one factor of the Racial Contract that is most prominent in making the Contract so powerful, yet almost entirely invisible to much of the country. This being, of course, the epistemological factors of the Racial Contract that form an “epistemology of ignorance”⁵⁶ amongst white people that facilitates the sort of “double-consciousness” that

⁵⁴ Charles W. Mills, *The Racial Contract*, (Ithaca, NY: Cornell University Press, 1997), 1.

⁵⁵ Mills, *The Racial Contract*, 7.

⁵⁶ Mills, *The Racial Contract*, 18.

W.E.B. Du Bois famously conceptualized in his classic *The Souls of Black Folk*.⁵⁷ The resulting epistemic privilege afforded to the oppressed and epistemic disadvantage of the oppressors are vital to one's understanding of the normative values of the Racial Contract.

I argue that theorizing a solution to oppression that is contingent upon epistemic division, such as the racial oppression as understood by Mills' Racial Contract, is best done by evaluating basic Marxist structures. By removing the primacy of class oppression from the basic structures of the Marxist argument, I will make the case for what I call *Epistemic Marxism* as a potential path for the dissolution of the Racial Contract. While doing so, I will demonstrate that such a conception which is dependent on basic Marxist structures is actually entirely compatible with Mills' largely liberal argument; this is because, while his argument uses the language of liberalism, it actually features many of the key components of Marxist ideology.⁵⁸

I will argue, however, that where Marx advocated for the violent revolution of the proletariat class, stemming from a widespread increase of class-consciousness, the issue of racial oppression will require an increase in *race-consciousness*. However, racial oppression cannot find its solution in widespread violent revolution, as I will demonstrate. Instead, in order to reveal the contradictions of the Racial Contract and revolutionize them in practice, we will need to raise an *ideological revolution*. Furthermore, my conception of an ideological revolution is, in fact, more in line with the "oppressive epistemic structure" that I will derive from Marx, and is

⁵⁷ W.E.B. Du Bois, "The Souls of Black Folk," in *The Souls of Black Folk by W.E.B. Du Bois: With a Critical Introduction by Patricia H. Hinchey*, ed. Patricia H. Hinchey, 1st ed., vol. 2 (Gorham, ME: Myers Education Press, 2018), 9.

⁵⁸ The most obvious example, which will not be discussed at length, being that Mills' Racial Contract is what he refers to as a "naturalized theory." By this, he means a theory that is established primarily through an account of historical actualities. As he points out in the chapter titled "'Ideal Theory' as Ideology" in his book *Black Rights/White Wrongs: The Critique of Racial Liberalism*, this is attributed directly to Marx's emphasis in *The German Ideology* on dealing with "real, active, [people]," not "[people] as narrated, thought of, imagined, conceived," but "as they *actually* are."

therefore both explanatorily and normatively superior to a violent revolution as a solution to racial oppression.

Mills points out that the Racial Contract contains an element that is unlike traditional social contracts, yet pivotal to one's understanding of its reality. This element is, of course, that the Racial Contract is also an epistemological contract. Mills concedes that other traditional contracts do contain epistemological requirements (with Hobbes, for instance, "the ability to assess the objectively optimal prudential course of action and what it requires of us for self-interested cooperation with others").⁵⁹ However, where the epistemological agreement differs from the traditional contract

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is that the Racial Contract requires an agreement to interpret the world that fundamentally *diverges* from reality. Rather than agreeing to an epistemological system of interpretation of reality, "one has an agreement to *misinterpret* the world."⁶⁰ This then creates an "epistemology of ignorance," resulting in "the ironic outcome that whites will in general be unable to understand the world they themselves have made."⁶¹

An important aspect of this is the way in which this epistemology is created intentionally by a powerful few, but followed ignorantly by the white masses. Indeed, he argues that "There will be white mythologies, invented Orients, invented Africas, invented Americas."⁶² And haven't we seen the realities of this notion? Haven't we seen the absence of history in our

⁵⁹ Mills, *The Racial Contract*, 17.

⁶⁰ Mills, *The Racial Contract*, 17-18.

⁶¹ Mills, *The Racial Contract*, 18.

⁶² Mills, *The Racial Contract*, 18.

schools regarding the atrocities of colonization? Haven't we seen the stories of the ways in which Native Americans were hunted and murdered be brushed over by the excuse that *they attacked first* as if their land had not first been invaded by the white man? Haven't we seen the fundamental erasure of the realities of slavery? What more evidence do we need for the intentional implementation of an epistemology of ignorance than the notion that the Civil War, resulting in the emancipation of slaves, was actually fought primarily due to the encroachment on "states' rights?"⁶³ Indeed, the narratives of racial oppression in our society are deeply manipulated by those most interested in maintaining the white polity, and that white polity has unintentionally been blinded by the most prominent *opiate of the masses ever to have existed*. Only, those affected by it exist on all areas of the class spectrum. The afflicted (that being the average member of the white polity), in this case, are not *materially* or *politically* disadvantaged, the reality is quite the opposite; instead, they are *epistemically* disadvantaged. A necessary but perilous feature of this epistemic disadvantage is that, unlike Marx's opiate of religion, the epistemically disadvantaged of the Racial Contract *are not even aware that they are parties to the contract*.

Furthermore, where there are epistemically disadvantaged groups, there are necessarily those who are epistemically privileged. The notion of nonwhite people being epistemically privileged is not one that is original to Mills' theory. Indeed, perhaps the most famous explanation of the concept comes from W.E.B. Du Bois who characterizes this as "double-consciousness," given only to those "born with a veil."⁶⁴ Ultimately, the epistemic privilege created by the Racial Contract naturally results in nonwhite people being acutely aware

⁶³ Frank James, "Slavery, Not States' Rights, Caused Civil War Whose Political Effects Linger," NPR (NPR, April 12, 2011),

<https://www.npr.org/sections/itsallpolitics/2011/04/12/135353655/slavery-not-states-rights-was-civil-wars-cause>.

⁶⁴ Du Bois, "The Souls of Black Folk," 9.

of the existence of the Racial Contract, whether or not they conceive of it in the same manner presented by Mills. In fact, it is this very epistemic privilege that leads to Mills' thesis that "The Racial Contract has always been recognized by nonwhites as the real moral/political agreement to be challenged."⁶⁵

The epistemology of ignorance that exists today focuses squarely around whether or not the Racial Contract exists at all. Indeed, as has been previously demonstrated, the narratives surrounding racial oppression have been so severely manipulated that the once overt formation of the Racial Contract during the era of slavery is, to most white Americans, entirely *invisible*. Perhaps the single-most prominent way in which the narratives surrounding racial oppression in the United States have been fundamentally manipulated is the clear misunderstanding of the meaning of race and racism. This is expertly laid out in the closing chapter of Mills' book. Race, in fact, is not biologically determined. Rather, race, separate from skin color which is biological, is the set of socially constructed relations *surrounding* skin color. This recognition allows Mills to separate (capital W) Whiteness from whiteness, where Whiteness represents, not a phenotypic skin color, "but a set of power relations."⁶⁶ Indeed, understanding of power differentials are pivotal to a realistic conception of racism. People who experience Whiteness are inherently unable to experience racism against them, as they are the beneficiaries of the Racial Contract. However, as suggested by the dichotomization between Whiteness as a sociopolitical construct and whiteness as a phenotypic skin color, the Racial Contract, and a socially constructed conception of race allow for what Mills refers to as "race traitors." This is, of course, because the goal of this conception of the Racial Contract and the fight to dismantle it, is not "to replace one Racial Contract with another of a different color but ultimately to eliminate race (not as innocent

⁶⁵ Mills, *The Racial Contract*, 109.

⁶⁶ Mills, *The Racial Contract*, 127.

human variety but as ontological superiority and inferiority, as differential entitlement and privilege) altogether.”⁶⁷

The epistemological factors of the Racial Contract are key when conceptualizing the argument through the lens of basic Marxist structures. Before turning our attention to these basic structures, it seems necessary to acknowledge the issue of Marx’s focus on class and how it affects a Marxist answer to the Racial Contract. Simply put, Marx can provide no satisfactory solution to the Racial Contract if one sticks to the hardline belief that the only significant axis of oppression is that of class oppression. For this reason, I argue that Marx’s view on class is a symptom of his epistemic disadvantage in regards to other axes of oppression. While Marx certainly has a level of awareness of other types of oppression such as the gender oppression of women in Bourgeois Capitalist society as discussed in the *Manifesto*⁶⁸, it seems clear that he is lacking a holistic understanding of this axis of oppression insofar as it comprises a domination contract. For this reason, I suggest that while traditional hardline Marxism is rather unhelpful as a solution to racial oppression, the basic structures of his theory of class oppression and how it can be dismantled are still quite applicable. Therefore, I ask the reader to think of Marxism, not as an answer to class oppression, but as an answer to the generic “domination contract.” In doing so, one will find that Marx, in fact, offers a very powerful starting point for the dismantling of the Racial Contract.

If Mills’ mention of “race traitors” sounds like the basic structures of the formation of Marx’s proletarian revolution, it’s because, for all intents and purposes, it is. Much like Marx, Mills requires the defection of members of the dominant group in order to begin the revolution that will eventually abolish the concept of the different groups altogether. However, it is

⁶⁷ Mills, *The Racial Contract*, 127.

⁶⁸ Karl Marx and Friedrich Engels, “Manifesto of the Communist Party,” in *The Marx-Engels Reader*, edited by Robert C. Tucker, 2nd ed. (New York, NY: Norton, 1978), 487-488.

important to note a few key differences between the two theories. Where Marx sees the

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Bourgeois “class traitors” as necessary to provide the initial push toward class-consciousness⁶⁹ for the proletariat in the larger goal of their revolution, the revolution within Mills’ theory begins and ends with the “race traitors.”⁷⁰ This is because race “as ontological superiority and inferiority” is entirely perpetuated by those who are White, whether or not they are

phenotypically white. Where the defectors for Marx are the beginning of the revolution, the defectors of the Racial Contract *are the revolution*.

Additionally, the goal of the Contract’s dissolution—that being not to replace the Racial Contract with another iteration in which nonwhite people are the dominant class, but rather to abolish the concept of race altogether—is also borrowed from Marx’s goals of the Proletariat revolution. The goal was not to simply form a new Bourgeois class from former Proletarians; rather, Marx envisioned the socialization of the means of production and the abolition of private property as a means to dissolving the social construct of class *altogether*.

Another way of conceiving of this is that the basic Marxist structure for dismantling systems of oppression calls for the raising of consciousness in whichever group is epistemically disadvantaged, this derived principle is what I refer to as the *oppressive epistemic structure*. In the case of Marx, the proletariat are disadvantaged insofar as they are lacking the necessary

⁶⁹ Karl Marx and Friedrich Engels, “Manifesto of the Communist Party,” in *The Marx-Engels Reader*, ed. Robert C. Tucker, 2nd ed. (New York, NY: Norton, 1978), pp. 473-500, 481.

⁷⁰ As has been theorized by G. A. Cohen, Marx saw the Proletariat revolution as inevitable “not whatever people might do, but because of what people, being rational, were bound, predictably, to do.” However, people, being rational, are not bound to do that of which they are unaware. For this reason, Bourgeois class traitors were necessary to provide the initial class-consciousness. From there, the domino-effect of people as predictable rational agents could progress.

class-consciousness to kick off the revolution. Again, this is why Marx claims that epistemically privileged Bourgeois class traitors, like himself, are necessary to give the proletariat the first push.⁷¹ The same structure is clearly present in the dismantling of the Racial Contract. The epistemically disadvantaged White people require *race-consciousness* to begin the revolution. It is important to note, however, that race-consciousness need not come from epistemically privileged nonwhite individuals,⁷² and would more realistically come from epistemically privileged white “race traitors,”⁷³ in clear keeping with the previously described structure. However, there are a number of reasons why this revolution is clearly *an ideological one*, rather than a violent revolution.

The first and most obvious being that this is clearly what is prescribed by the Racial Contract itself. The entire Contract is held together, for the most part, by the epistemology of ignorance. If the ignorance is eventually pulled away, all that will remain is those who are aware of the Contract and defect against it, and those who are aware of the Contract and choose to

⁷¹ Whether or not the Bourgeois are epistemically privileged is not something you will find explicitly mentioned in Marx’s works. However, Marx’s prescription of the Bourgeois class traitor’s role in providing the initial class-consciousness required to begin the proletariat revolution is immediate evidence of this feature. How should the Bourgeois defector provide consciousness of the proletariat class to the proletarian if they do not, themselves, hold this consciousness? It seems quite clear that they cannot. Further, the lack of class-consciousness amongst the Proletariat comprises clear epistemic disadvantage, this claim is uncontested.

⁷² It seems necessary to mention that it isn’t only unnecessary that it not come from nonwhite individuals, but that it would be wrong to expect it of nonwhite individuals. Because of the epistemological features of the Racial Contract, epistemically disadvantaged White individuals are necessarily predisposed to reject arguments for the Racial Contract when coming from nonwhite individuals. Beyond this, nonwhite individuals, who have been the subject of historical oppression as a result of the Racial Contract, cannot and should not be expected to be the sole arbiters of its dissolution. We cannot expect the oppressed to be responsible for their liberation, it is the responsibility of the oppressor to end their oppressive behavior. That being said, the promise of liberation would certainly provide motivation for the involvement of willing nonwhite individuals. However, by keeping the focus of the action on white individuals operating in the circles of other white individuals to end their oppressive behavior, this structure avoids the sort of “white-saviorism” that has pervaded many more recent theories of progress in racial oppression. It should be clear that the Epistemic Marxist structure applied to racial oppression is not a theory focused on “saving nonwhite people through the generous action of white individuals,” rather, its focus is on confronting and ending a history of ignorant and oppressive behavior perpetuated by white people as a group.

⁷³ Apart from the argument in the previous footnote, it may be the case that the first epistemically privileged “race traitor” may require race-consciousness to come from an epistemically privileged nonwhite individual. However, this could very well be through the consultation of established academic works such as Mills’ book. I consider my own experience to be an example of this, as my first occasion of clear race-consciousness came as a result of Bryan Stevenson’s *Just Mercy*. Ever since then, education on race has been one of, if not, the primary focus of my educational endeavors.

uphold it. As for which of those two groups would be most prominent, it seems clear that the former, rather than the latter, would comprise the majority.

This much seems clear from Mills' argument for the White ignorance being a willing ignorance. This willing ignorance is one in which White individuals turn away from confronting the realities of the Racial Contract because it is easier or more comfortable than acknowledging the existence of systemic racism. In doing this, they are able to remain in the comfort of their ignorance. But if we suppose that those who prefer to remain in the comfort of their ignorance, in fact, support and wish to uphold systemic oppression, what motivation would they have for hiding it? In recent history we have seen that outward racism has become more normalized in public, politics, and law, even if it comprises a minority view. The difficult reality is that those who outspokenly support the Racial Contract have indeed achieved a higher level of epistemic privilege than those who remain in their willing ignorance; this is because they have come to realize the existence of systemic oppression under the Racial Contract, yet choose to support it for the potential of disproportionate material benefit.⁷⁴

What position is left for those that remain in the comfort of their willing ignorance? It would seem that their unwillingness to confront the realities of the Racial Contract is an unwillingness to accept that they are complicit in a system of injustice. However, if they were forced to confront their ignorance through mounting prominence of discussions of the realities of the Racial Contract by means of an ideological revolution, it stands to reason that their

⁷⁴ The epistemic privilege achieved by the supporters of the Contract is, of course, not a complete epistemic privilege. The views of white-supremacists are often upheld or justified by ignorant and fallacious racists arguments. However, so too are the justifications for the non-existence of racism often offered by the willingly ignorant. Therefore, the decision to boldly say "systemic racism exists, and I support it" is, in a way, further down the road of progress toward epistemic privilege than those who maintain its non-existence. The primary difference is that white-supremacist individuals, while recognizing a system of oppression, have chosen to reject key normative principles, namely the equal worth of all persons, in favor of the promise of material benefit.

unwillingness to be complicit in a system of injustice would carry through, even if it is more laborious than their previously ignorant stance.

Beyond this, to willingly and knowingly stand in favor of the Racial Contract would be to stand against the values which the United States purports to uphold. Intrinsic in the Racial Contract is the rejection of equality of opportunity and of outcome, the former being a key value of the United States, and the latter being a natural result of the *actual* presence of the former.⁷⁵ While it is abundantly clear that, throughout its existence, the United States has failed to live up to these values for even *a single day*, they are still widely believed to be American values, and are therefore given a certain credence and reality.

Therefore, having established that the vast majority of the Contract's beneficiaries would willingly defect from the Contract, the ideological revolution would be nearly won. The remaining minority, composed of those who failed to reject the Contract, would then enter a phase in which they would attempt in vain to reestablish the dominance of the Racial Contract through further manipulation of the narratives of racial oppression. Should their attempts, in fact, be in vain, the result will be a society composed entirely of epistemically privileged individuals,

⁷⁵ While not essential to this argument, it seems abundantly clear that true equality of opportunity naturally leads to equality of outcome. This certainly is not always the case when viewed on an atomistic level; it is true that some individuals' poor decisions lead to poor outcomes, even if their opportunities were equivalent to their peers. However, when viewed on a societal level, it becomes incredibly clear that the disparities amongst various axes of oppression in the United States demonstrate the inequality of opportunity. To contend that true equality of opportunity has been achieved within the nation would be to contend that entire groups of people who are born into and remain in positions of disadvantage do so as a result of their poor choices, whereas the privileged few who are born into and remain in positions of power do so as a result of their superior decision making. This is demonstrably false. To put it more simply, to acknowledge that equality of opportunity does not exist is to merely acknowledge that many people are born into many different situations, some include more privilege, some less. Indeed, if true equality of process had been achieved, it seems self-evident that, when viewed on a societal scale which allows for the few outliers, statistical equality of outcome would follow. Therefore, the clear presence of massive inequality in the United States demonstrates the absence of both equality of opportunity and outcome. I propose this is an extension of the "restrictive view" of legal ideology proposed by Crenshaw in her essay *Race, Reform, and Retrenchment*, which focuses on preventing future inequalities without addressing the history of the same inequalities. Crenshaw argues that this results in the color-blind society; I argue that the same principle applied to legal ideology at large results in equality of outcome that exists only in name, but not in reality.

entirely conscious of the now dismantled Racial Contract. As previously suggested by Mills, the result would be the withering away of race “as ontological superiority and inferiority” altogether.

This clearly tracks with Marx’s parallel view that after having won the violent proletariat revolution, there would be a mass socialization of the means of production and redistribution of wealth. During this time, the remaining Bourgeois would fight in vain to reverse the revolution. However, so long as their attempts remain in vain, the natural progression of society is the gradual dissolution of class structure and government altogether.

Beyond this, there are clear reasons why a violent revolution would not be successful in achieving the dismantling of the Racial Contract. The most prominent among these is laid out by Edward Said. In an interview conducted in 1998 entitled “On Orientalism,” Said discussed an important consequence of his theory of Orientalism. He argues that violence perpetrated by nonwhite individuals result in notions of radicalization being ascribed to all members of the group. This, he argues, is most clearly evident by the massive rise in Islamophobia following the 1997 bombing of the World Trade Center. While the individual who perpetuated this attack did, in fact, subscribe to radical religious views, it is clearly fallacious to ascribe those same views to all members of the same religion. He provides a helpful comparison. Contrast the previous example with the failure of the same generalizations to be made of White Christian nationalists following Timothy McVeigh’s bombing of the Alfred P. Murrah Federal Building in Oklahoma City in 1995.⁷⁶ Of course, it must be noted that this is no accident, rather a very key feature of the Racial Contracts epistemological factors acting as a way to ideologically condition and justify violence that is necessary in reinforcing the Contract, as suggested by Mills.⁷⁷

⁷⁶ Edward Said, “On Orientalism,” Interview by Sut Jhally, *Media Education Foundation*, 1998 Northampton, MA, 7-8.

⁷⁷ Mills, *The Racial Contract*, 81.

Given this notion, it seems quite clear that even a small group forming a violent revolution against the white polity could be met with overwhelmingly brutal retaliation. Further, there is no guarantee that this retaliation would end with only the perpetrators of the revolution. This is not only a theoretical possibility, but a historical actuality that manifested in the aftermath of Nat Turner's rebellion, when many innocent black people were lynched as reprisals for the rebellion.⁷⁸ This, in conjunction with the fact that in the United States, nonwhite people make up a minority of the population nationally, but also a vast minority in most regions, makes the realistic success of a violent revolution very miniscule.

It is also worth noting that a violent method by no means guarantees the dissolution of race and the Racial Contract, but, if successful, would likely replace it with another Racial Contract resulting in the subjugation of phenotypically white individuals. This is because race, while socially constructed, is still inherently tied to biologically determined skin color. Simply removing the dominant race from power does not resolve the power differential issue created by race, rather, it simply reverses the power differential. *The only way to dismantle the Racial Contract is through the widespread increase of race-consciousness resulting in the dissolution of the epistemology of ignorance and thereby the racial power differential.* This fundamentally differs from Marx's conception of *class*, as class is not something that is tied to biologically phenotypic characteristics as is race. Therefore, by socializing the means of production and redistributing the wealth, the class structure is fundamentally disrupted. However, violent revolution and the removal of white people as the dominant group does not fundamentally disrupt the Racial Contract or the notion of Whiteness as a sociopolitical reality.

⁷⁸ History.com Editors, "Nat Turner Executed in Virginia," HISTORY (A&E Television Networks, February 9, 2010).

In fact, when evaluating these basic structures of Marxism in comparison to other axes of oppression (oppression of gender, sex, sexuality, etc.), it seems abundantly clear that class is the exception rather than the rule, insofar as it is the only axis of oppression that is alterable to the oppressed party. In the case of these other axes of oppression, the ideological revolution model is superior, as the primary solution to their respective domination contracts is *universal epistemic privilege*. Compare this to oppression of class, where universal epistemic privilege fails to, by itself, resolve the primary inequalities of its respective domination contract, that being Bourgeois Capitalism. This is because these axes of oppression are *primarily* ideological with material consequences, whereas oppression of class only exists insofar as it materially exists. Without material inequality, there can exist no such thing as oppression of class. Inversely, without material inequality, there certainly can exist oppression of race, sexuality, gender, and so on. This demonstrates that Marx's claim that these other axes of oppression were purely superstructural is markedly false, further showing his epistemic disadvantage in regards to those axes of oppression. Put more simply, in the case of racial oppression, if the epistemic division is resolved, the dissolution of the resulting material inequalities will follow; the same, however, is not true of class. In the case of class, if the material inequalities are resolved, the dissolution of the epistemic division will follow.

From this, we may conclude that for all axes of oppression with the exception of class *epistemic division* is both conceptually and temporally primary, with material inequalities being a secondary result of the primary inequality. Nowhere is this stated more clearly than Mills' own proto-Hobbes-Rousseauian conception of race and the white polity in his article "Body Politic, Bodies Impolitic." Mills focuses on Rousseau's conception of the origin of inequality, that being the notion that once the first individual claimed an item as their own, thus establishing private

property, and the others believed them, equality was doomed, thus forming the domination contract of class oppression.⁷⁹ Mills uses this notion to establish that, similarly, when the first white person proclaimed the sub-personhood of nonwhite people and the other white people believed them, the domination contract of racial oppression was formed.⁸⁰ From this it is clear that, in the first case, it was the material inequality that allowed the epistemic division of class to exist. First, the person had to have the item, then they persuaded others to believe that it was theirs. In the case of racial oppression, first it had to be believed that nonwhite people were subhuman, then material inequality could ensue.

It should be noted, however, that while epistemic division is primary with respect to the origination of these axes of oppression as well as its dissolution, the material inequalities are no less significant in its continuance. Utilizing the traditional base and superstructure model prescribed by Marxism, we can then establish that in all axes of oppression with the exception of class, it is actually the epistemic division that forms the base, with the material inequalities comprising the superstructure. This fits naturally into the base-superstructure formula, as it is clear that the superstructural material inequalities help to shape and maintain the base of epistemic division, which naturally reinforces the material inequalities.

Because of the primacy of epistemic division, an ideological revolution, as opposed to a violent revolution, is explanatorily superior as it clearly provides a more successful process to achieve the desired goal of the fundamental dissolution of the concept of race “as ontological superiority and inferiority.” Beyond this, a violent revolution in this scenario would actually

⁷⁹ Jean-Jacques Rousseau, “Discourse on the Origin of Inequality,” in *The Basic Political Writings: Discourse on the Sciences and the Arts, Discourse on the Origin of Inequality, Discourse on Political Economy, On the Social Contract, the State of War*, ed. Donald A. Cress (Indianapolis, IN: Hackett Publishing Company, Inc, 1998), pp. 37-81, 65.

⁸⁰ Charles W. Mills, “Body Politic, Bodies Impolitic,” *Social Research* 78, no. 2 (2011): 583–606, <http://www.jstor.org/stable/23347191>, 8-11.

contradict the derived oppressive epistemic structure, as in the case of a violent racial revolution, the epistemically privileged would wage war upon the disadvantaged. This would be fundamentally counter to the previously described epistemic structure.

In addition, the ideological revolution is *normatively* superior. This is quite clear when Mills says “The ‘Racial Contract’ thus places itself within the sensible mainstream of moral theory by not holding people responsible for what they cannot help,” namely their phenotypic skin color.⁸¹ A violent racial revolution would, in fact, hold phenotypically white people

accountable for their skin being white, something beyond their control. Furthermore, since the majority of the white polity are entirely unaware of their complicity in the Racial Contract, even if this ignorance contains a certain level of intentionality, as a result of its epistemological value, it would be normatively unacceptable to hold them accountable for their unknowing participation through violence. Compare this to the *ideological* revolution, in which no phenotypically white person is held accountable for the color of their skin, as the revolution begins and ends with their becoming conscious

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of the realities of the Racial Contract and their willing rejection thereof. That being said, it seems clear that those who fail to reject the Racial Contract and respond violently certainly can be held accountable. This is because they would be held responsible for something that is well within their control, namely both their unwillingness to reject the Racial Contract, and their violent response.

⁸¹ Mills, *The Racial Contract*, 126.

Mills' theory of a Racial Contract is thoroughly convincing. His argument for the Contract creating an "epistemology of ignorance" is an incredibly helpful tool in explaining both racism as a historical actuality and a current political system. In fact, it is the Contract's epistemological value that is most pivotal in the maintenance of the Contract as it exists today, unlike the Racial Contract of the era of slavery in the United States, which was mostly maintained by its exploitative values. While Mills masterfully presents the issue of the Racial Contract in traditionally liberal language, it seems that basic Marxist structures are clearly underlying his conception of a resolution of the Racial Contract. However, where Marx claimed that all history is "the history of class struggles," I advocate that all history is a history of epistemic division. Therefore, the best way of conceiving of the various axes of oppression and their ultimate dissolution is through what I call *Epistemic Marxism*. It then follows that the only viable method by which the Racial Contract may be dismantled is through an *ideological* revolution that can be easily conceptualized using basic Marxist structures and derived principles. This *should not* be confused with the violent revolution present in Marx's own theory for the dismantling of Bourgeois Capitalism. Such a violent revolution, applied to the issue of racial oppression, would not only be unsuccessful, but would actually contradict many of the basic tenets of the Marxist structure, most notably the oppressive epistemic structure. Indeed, as I have demonstrated, an *ideological* revolution is not only compatible with basic Marxist structures, but is both explanatorily and normatively superior to a violent revolution as a means to resolving systemic oppression.